

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING WILD CICHORIUM INTYBUS WITH DRUGS IN THE TREATMENT OF DIABETES

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Abstract. Long-term consumption of any chemical drug obtained by synthesis in the current environmental environment causes various complications in living organisms. In particular, since almost all of the drugs used in the treatment of diabetes have side effects, first of all, taking into account the patient's misogyny, foods and drugs that increase the activity of the pancreas and provide energy to the body in exchange for the biological breakdown of sugar in the blood it is necessary to know how to use plants together correctly. Examples of such plants are Jerusalem artichoke, chamomile, ginger, and medicinal plants.

Аннотация. Длительное употребление любого химического препарата, полученного путем синтеза в современной экологической среде, вызывает различные осложнения в живых организмах. В частности, поскольку практически все препараты, используемые при лечении диабета, имеют побочные эффекты, в первую очередь с учетом женоненавистничества пациента, продукты и препараты, повышающие активность поджелудочной железы и обеспечивающие организм энергией в обмен на биологическое расщепление сахара в крови необходимо знать, как правильно употреблять растения вместе. Примерами таких растений являются топинамбур, ромашка, имбирь и лекарственные растения.

Purpose of the inspection:

A data-driven study of the side effects of drugs used in the treatment of diabetes and the results obtained when they are used in combination with drugs, among possible medicinal plants.

Material and methods: The study was conducted using medical records of 1113 patients at the Fergana Endocrinology Hospital in January-June. The age of patients ranges from 13 to 70 years and older. The average age of the patients was about 52 years, of which 327 (29%) were men and 786 (71%) women. When studying the drugs used in their treatment, it became known that the following drugs are used.

Currently, in the treatment of patients with diabetes, depending on the condition of the disease, the following drugs are prescribed.

1. Biguanides: Sifor, Bagomet, Metformin acid, Glucophage, Metfogamma. These drugs prevent the absorption of glucose in the intestines, saturate the tissues of the body with sugar;

2. Sulfoarea drugs: Tolbutamide, glibenclamide. These drugs improve the synthesis of glucose by the tissues of the pancreas and its cells, and also help the absorption of sugar in the tissues;

3. Inhibitors of alpha-glucosidases: Acarbose improves insulin synthesis, prevents a sharp increase in sugar levels.

4. Meglitinides: Prandin (repaglinide) and Starlix (nateglinide) these drugs lower blood glucose levels;

5. Thiazolidinediones: Actrapid Penfill reduces the level of glucose produced in the liver.

When the side effects of these drugs were studied, the following information was revealed.

The following side effects may occur with the medications used:

Medicines	Sifor	Glibenklamid	Akarboza	Meglitinid	Aktrapid
Side effects					
Stomach discomfort, indigestion, diarrhea and loss of appetite.	+	+	+	-	-
Taste disturbances metallic taste	+	-	-	-	-
Lactic acidosis	+	+	-	-	-
Allergic reactions	+	+	+	+	+
From the endocrine system	-	+	-	-	-
Megaloblastic anemia	-	-	+	-	-
The development of hepatitis is liver failure;	+	+	-	+	+
Diabetic precoma,	+	+	-	+	-
From the central nervous system	-	+	+	-	+
Immune system disorders	-	-	+	-	+
Kidney failure or impaired kidney function	+	+	-	+	+
Leukopenia.	-	+	-	-	-
Gaining weight	-	-	-	-	+
Increased risk of bladder cancer	-	-	-	-	+
Hypoglycemia undefined	-	-	-	+	+
Diabetic neuropathy	-	-	-	-	+

+ the presence of a side effect

- the absence of a side effect.

In the treatment of diabetes mellitus, it is necessary to correctly recommend medicines, food additives and tinctures depending on the level of the disease. First of all, the patient's personality is taken into account, and it is recommended to use the following foods and food supplements that increase the activity of the pancreas and provide energy to the body due to the biological breakdown of sugar in the blood.

Recommendation 1:		It is effective to take 1 pumpkin, dry it, grind it into a powder and eat 6 grams 3 times.
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<p>Recommendation 2:</p>		<p>It is also useful to take 20 - 30 pieces of grapes and crush them and chew them half an hour before meals.</p>
<p>Recommendation 3:</p>		<p>Boil 50 g of barley in 2 liters of water over low heat until half a liter remains, then eat the barley and drink the water. Its seeds and bark have been used since ancient times to improve and normalize blood glucose levels.</p>
<p>Recommendation 4:</p>		<p>Drinking 100-200 ml of whey 1-2 times a day is also beneficial.</p>
<p>Recommendation 5:</p>		<p>You can drink 20 grams of plum pulp in boiling water as tea.</p>
<p>Recommendation 6:</p>		<p>10 grams of corn kernels, 10 grams of pomegranate flowers, and 10 grams of basil should be drunk together.</p>
<p>Recommendation 7:</p>		<p>It gives good results even if in the summer season it is eaten in salads made from dandelion, nettle, and Cicorium intybus.</p>
<p>Recommendation 8:</p>		<p>The stems and roots of the wild gorse are collected and dried in the summer months. Make a powder from it, infuse 2 spoons in boiling water and drink 3 times a day.</p>

The main effect of all the above methods is to regulate the level of glucose in the blood and, if necessary, bring it down to standard values. In addition, they perfectly stimulate the liver and kidneys, increase the efficiency of the cardiovascular system. Such recipes are actively used in the treatment of type 2 diabetes, and at the same time, you can avoid taking medications.

Studies: Among the types of mushroom, Zangori mushroom, which grows wild, was chosen for the study. Because this species is common in the Fergana Valley, it is planted among the crops in the field, along the road, from the middle of summer. we can see on the banks and along the ditches. Zangori sachratki is a plant belonging to the family of sedges. It is the only species of the sachratki family that grows in Uzbekistan. All the flowers in the sachratki basket are blue and bisexual. The sachratki is a medicinal plant. Medicines prepared from its root, leaves and stem during flowering are used to treat gastrointestinal diseases. The above-ground part of the stem is harvested from the bottom of the stem before the leaf, the easiest and simplest way is to dry it under natural conditions, protected from sunlight. It is beneficial to wash the dried stalks and drink them instead of dry tea in boiling water that is not very hot, i.e., not exceeding 50 degrees Celsius. if done, the benefits will increase even more.

It was studied its use among the people. When 80 patients who came to the medical institution in Cnust district of Namangan province, medicinal herbs, and more precisely, the wild growing Zangori sachratki plant and its level of use were studied using a questionnaire, 89 % of patients said that they use naturally growing medicinal plants such as Namatak, kiyikoti, frankincense, marigold, sachartki and other medicinal plants.

Composition of Cicorium intybus:

1. 49%-75% inulin content in the stem of Cicorium intybus;
2. Jerusalem artichoke contains 14% inulin;
3. 16% insulin in garlic;
4. Onion contains 2-6% inulin;
5. 0.5-1% inulin in barley;
6. The spike contains 0.5-1.5% inulin.

Inulin is an organic substance that belongs to the group of polysaccharides and is a polymer of D-fructose. Inulin is an organic, natural substance that can replace insulin secreted from the back of the pancreas. Inulin plays an important role in the conversion of glucose into glycogen and can replace insulin.

Cicorium intybus also contains 17% - 20% carotene. Carotene is considered the basis of vitamin A. Carotene benefits the human body, skin integrity, mucous membrane integrity, eye health. B-carotene in the mushroom plant improves lung strength.

Tannins help to bind collagen proteins, it increases the strength of the skin and makes it more resistant. The most important benefit of tannins is that they protect the plant. Due to the fact that it gives a rough mass to the stem of the plant, it reduces the desire to consume it.

The plant contains up to 4% protein. If an adult human body has 80-120 high-quality protein compounds in its daily diet, it will provide an opportunity for the daily functioning of the vital organs of the body. We can say that we cannot replace the necessary mass with the plant we eat, but it is clear that the protein contained in the sprout is an addition to the protein consumed by us with other products, which is among the quality proteins.

The choline content of Cicorium intybus is very different from that of other plants. We know that choline is one of the group B vitamins. The choline contained in the bark prevents the liver from becoming fatty and improves the physiology of the blood-forming organs. The plant contains Vitamins A, B, C, E. Microelements K, Mg, Fe. It is not for nothing that scholars say that our country is a paradise. In our country, plants with all useful properties are not found in other regions. The presence of 4 seasons in this heavenly place, which is given by

Allah, allows the plant to grow. How many useful roofs are there in one mushroom plant that we have discussed above. Knowing this, we medical workers should take natural treatment measures without using chemical preparations produced in various foreign countries.

Conclusions: Lowering blood sugar levels is a priority to prevent serious complications from diabetes. Therefore, we need to explain to the patient the need to control the sugar value himself. In addition, it is necessary to carry out explanatory work about prevention, about proper nutrition and optimal physical exercises. In addition, along with medicines, the patient's mood is taken into account, and in return for the biological breakdown of sugar in the blood, which leads to increased activity of the pancreas and the body the use of energy-giving foods and food supplements should be recommended. Depending on the results obtained, it is necessary to conduct research on this plant and, if necessary, apply it to medicine.

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